

Multifractal Detrended Fluctuation Analysis applied to center of pressure-based postural assessment in pregnant

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Abstract— Several physical and biological changes occur during pregnancy. Among these changes, the adjustment of postural control to maintain postural balance is a strategy adopted to decrease the risk of falling. The purpose of this study was to investigate the potential of fractal properties of the center of pressure sway to detect differences between non-pregnant and pregnant women on the first and third trimesters of pregnancy in the open and closed eye conditions. The multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis technique was used to extract the main fractal features. In both conditions, significant differences were found between non-pregnant and pregnant women in the third trimester. The analysis also showed a greater dependence on visual information in pregnant women, confirming the relevance of this sensory information as a strategy to maintain postural control.

Keywords — *Fractal properties, Multifractal spectrum pregnancy, Hurst exponent.*

I. Introduction

Throughout pregnancy, pregnant women undergo physical and biological changes [1]–[4]. In extreme cases, these changes can cause complications such as increased risk of falling due to reduced postural balance and musculoskeletal alterations [5], [6]. In addition, long-term memory loss due to hormonal action on the hippocampus [3], and severe cardiac arrhythmia due to increased plasma volume [4] can occur.

From a biomechanical point of view, several studies have sought to understand the changes in postural control and gait during pregnancy [7]–[11]. Also, studies have showed that visual information is essential for maintaining postural control in pregnant women [12]. In such studies, the center of pressure (COP) sway has been widely explored for the analysis of postural balance in pregnant women using equipment such as stabilometry [7], instrumented insole [13], force platform [8] and GAITRite [14].

The objective of the present study is to analyze the fractal characteristics of COP sway collected from the force platform

in groups of non-pregnant women (CT) and pregnant women with one (P1T) and three (P3T) trimesters of pregnancy, allowing to reveal structural and temporal information that cannot be obtained using conventional methods such as ellipse confidence area, total excursion or mean signal amplitude. Unlike Martinez-Marti [15], our study includes the control group and checks the COP only in the stand condition, also assessing whether fractal characteristics can reveal the effects that vision exerts on postural control in the different phases of gestation.

In the present study was used the multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis (MFDFA) technique presented by [16] to better understand the multifractal behavior of the COP signals. The MFDFA is able to answer if there is a long correlation interval of the COP time series for the analyzed groups in different time scales. Our hypothesis is that the fractal properties extracted from the COP are able to reveal alterations in postural control between the groups, especially in women in advanced gestational period, and that they may also indicate postural changes with the absence of visual information. Furthermore, we believe that the scale exponent is directly related to a detrimental change of postural stability.

II. Methods

A. Participants

Data from a previous study was re-analyzed [8]. Twenty-eight women, 13 pregnant (25.84 ± 4.65 years; 1.62 ± 0.05 m) and 15 non-pregnant (27.73 ± 5.51 years; 1.61 ± 0.06 m) participated in the study. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and all protocols were approved by the local Ethics Committee. All subjects signed a consent form before the experiment. The data from the pregnant women were collected in two sessions: (i) in the first trimester; and (ii) in the third trimester of pregnancy (between 28 to 40 weeks).

B. Protocol

Participants stood upright on a force platform (Model OR6-7, AMTI, USA) operating at 100 Hz. Each subject was instructed to stand still on the force platform (with feet ~20 cm apart) and arms along the body. Markings were made around each participant's foot on a paper fixed to the force platform to control foot position between trials in both experimental sessions (e.g., first and third trimester). Each subject performed three 60s trials with eyes open (OE condition), focusing on a target positioned ~2m in front of them, and three 60s trials with eyes closed (CE condition). A period of 2 min of rest between each trial was adopted to avoid muscle fatigue [19]. Force and moment were used to calculate the displacement of the COP in the anterior-posterior (AP) and medial-lateral (ML) directions according to the method described in [17].

C. MFDFA calculation

Before performing a fractal analysis, it is important to consider the nature of the signal [18]. A stationarity test (KPSS) was performed as DFA is sensitive to this feature. In addition, the mean, standard deviation, autocorrelation and first-order difference were evaluated to verify if the signal present a correlated structure.

The MFDFA technique was applied in the COP time series in the AP and ML directions to observe their correlation properties. This method was proposed by [19] and it is an adaptation of the DFA to identify the behavior of multifractal scales in a time series. A full and detailed description on how to calculate MFDFA can be found in [16].

D. Statistical Analysis

The normal distribution of the results was evaluated by the Shapiro-Wilk test ($p > 0.05$). Statistical comparisons were performed using mixed repeated measure ANOVA, with two factors: eye condition (OE and CE) and group (CT, P1T and P3T). Bonferroni's post hoc test was conducted if significant differences in the factors were found. Statistical analysis was performed in JASP software (version 0.17.3) with a significance level set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

III. Results

The COP time series for all groups revealed to have a non-stationary trend. Observing their autocorrelation and the first-order difference, it is possible to notice that these data have a random walk distribution, also explained by [20].

Regarding the fractal properties of the signal, it was observed that the data are characterized by Brownian motion. According to [21], if the original data is considered a random walk, then the integration of the original data, first step in MFDFA calculation, is not necessary.

Scale exponent values for $q = 2$ were statistically compared. The average of the scale exponent from the three trials was calculated for each individual in the OE and CE conditions. The scale exponent showed a significant main effect of group only for COP AP. The simple main effect of group was only significant for COP AP in all eye conditions (OE and CE). Regarding the simple main effect of eye conditions, there was a significant difference for all groups

for COP AP, and only for CT and P3T groups for COP ML.

The post hoc tests revealed that CT and P3T groups have a significant difference in AP direction for both eye conditions (OE and CE, $p = 0.014$ and $p = 0.006$ respectively). The results using the scale exponent identified a postural change along pregnancy (AP direction) and demonstrated the importance of visual information in postural control (AP and ML directions).

IV. Discussion

In the present study, we investigated the fractal properties of COP sway in non-pregnant and pregnant women on first and third trimesters while standing on a force platform under eyes open and eyes closed conditions. The displacement of the COP in both the AP and ML directions was analyzed. The results confirm our two hypotheses. The fractal properties were able to reveal a difference in postural control between non-pregnant women and women with advanced pregnancy (3 trimesters) in the AP direction. They were also able to identify a postural difference in the absence of visual information in all groups in the AP direction and in the CT and P3T groups in the ML direction. However, COP sway in standing position do not exhibit multifractal properties.

The values of the scale exponent H_q (Table 1) reveals that the analyzed signals presented a long-term correlation. The higher the H_q , the more persistent the signal, and this persistence in the COP scale exponent has an interpretation from a physiological point of view, more precisely in the mechanisms of postural control. Collins et al [22] suggests that the greater the persistence of the scale exponent of the COP, the greater the effort of muscle activity due to the decline in postural stability.

The results revealed that the fractal properties obtained by processing the MFDFA calculation on the COP signals extracted in the CT, P1T and P3T groups and in all directions (AP and ML) and conditions (OE and CE) meet monofractal characteristics. This means that only one scale exponent is enough to characterize the long-term correlation properties of the analyzed signals.

The main effect of group in the AP direction showed significant differences between the CT and P3T groups for both eye conditions. There was an increase in H_q in the AP direction as the pregnancy progresses. This agrees with our hypothesis that the fractal properties of COP sway can reveal changes in postural control throughout pregnancy and also indicate significant differences in postural control with the absence of visual information.

Our findings revealed that non-pregnant and pregnant women present significant differences regarding the COP fractal properties. The COP fractal properties of all groups show a monofractal behavior and the long-term correlation properties are more persistent throughout pregnancy. Furthermore, pregnant women demand greater visual dependence for postural control. These characteristics were more evident in the anteroposterior direction.

Future studies can assess how changes of the COP fractal properties explored in this study can contribute to the identification of possible pathologies and contribute to the proposal of intelligent systems that can assist the healthcare professional in the clinical setting.

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References

- [1] E. C. Fries and F. A. Hellebrandt, “The influence of pregnancy on the location of the center of gravity, postural stability, and body alignment,” *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 374–380, Sep. 1943, doi: 10.1016/S0002-9378(43)90431-4.
- [2] R. K. Jensen, S. Doucet, and T. Treitz, “Changes in segment mass and mass distribution during pregnancy,” *J Biomech*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 251–256, Feb. 1996, doi: 10.1016/0021-9290(95)00042-9.
- [3] M. Brett, “Motherhood and memory: a review,” *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 339–362, May 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0306-4530(01)00003-8.
- [4] A. Morton, “Physiological Changes and Cardiovascular Investigations in Pregnancy,” *Heart Lung Circ*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. e6–e15, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.hlc.2020.10.001.
- [5] J. Borg-Stein and S. A. Dugan, “Musculoskeletal Disorders of Pregnancy, Delivery and Postpartum,” *Phys Med Rehabil Clin N Am*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 459–476, Aug. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.pmr.2007.05.005.
- [6] J. L. McCrory, A. J. Chambers, A. Daftary, and M. S. Redfern, “Dynamic postural stability during advancing pregnancy,” *J Biomech*, vol. 43, no. 12, pp. 2434–2439, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.jbiomech.2009.09.058.
- [7] L. F. Oliveira, T. M. M. Vieira, A. R. Macedo, D. M. Simpson, and J. Nadal, “Postural sway changes during pregnancy: A descriptive study using stabilometry,” *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, vol. 147, no. 1, pp. 25–28, Nov. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ejogrb.2009.06.027.
- [8] L. S. Moreira, L. A. Elias, A. B. Gomide, M. F. Vieira, and W. N. Do Amaral, “A longitudinal assessment of myoelectric activity, postural sway, and Low-Back pain during pregnancy,” *Acta Bioeng Biomech*, vol. 19, no. 3, 2017, doi: 10.5277/ABB-00753-2016-02.
- [9] M. Branco, R. Santos-Rocha, and F. Vieira, “Biomechanics of Gait during Pregnancy,” *The Scientific World Journal*, vol. 2014, pp. 1–5, 2014, doi: 10.1155/2014/527940.
- [10] J. Bertuit, C. Leyh, M. Rooze, and V. Feipel, “Pregnancy-related changes in center of pressure during gait,” *Acta Bioeng Biomech*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 95–102, 2017.
- [11] R. D. Catena, J. P. Bailey, N. Campbell, B. C. Stewart, and S. J. Marion, “Correlations between joint kinematics and dynamic balance control during gait in pregnancy,” *Gait Posture*, vol. 80, pp. 106–112, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.gaitpost.2020.05.025.
- [12] E. E. Butler, I. Colón, M. L. Druzina, and J. Rose, “Postural equilibrium during pregnancy: Decreased stability with an increased reliance on visual cues,” *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, vol. 195, no. 4, pp. 1104–1108, Oct. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2006.06.015.
- [13] Y. Zhang, H. Lu, Y. Gu, and N. Hu, “Characteristics of the centre of pressure progression for pregnant women during walking,” *Int J Biomed Eng Technol*, vol. 17, no. 4, p. 387, 2015, doi: 10.1504/IJBET.2015.069406.
- [14] J. Bertuit, C. Leyh, M. Rooze, and V. Feipel, “Plantar Pressure During Gait in Pregnant Women,” *J Am Podiatr Med Assoc*, vol. 106, no. 6, pp. 398–405, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.7547/15-064.
- [15] F. Martínez-Martí, M. S. Martínez-García, M. Á. Carvajal, A. J. Palma, M. Anguiano, and A. M. Lallena, “Fractal behavior of the trajectories of the foot centers of pressure during pregnancy,” *Biomed Phys Eng Express*, vol. 5, no. 2, p. 025007, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1088/2057-1976/aaf0f3.
- [16] E. A. F. Ihlen, “Introduction to Multifractal Detrended Fluctuation Analysis in Matlab,” *Front Physiol*, vol. 3, 2012, doi: 10.3389/fphys.2012.00141.
- [17] D. A. Winter, A. E. Patla, M. Ishac, and W. H. Gage, “Motor mechanisms of balance during quiet standing,” *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 49–56, Feb. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S1050-6411(02)00085-8.
- [18] A. Eke *et al.*, “Physiological time series: Distinguishing fractal noises from motions,” *Pflugers Arch*, vol. 439, no. 4, 2000, doi: 10.1007/s004240050957.
- [19] J. W. Kantelhardt, S. A. Zschiegner, E. Koscielny-Bunde, S. Havlin, A. Bunde, and H. E. Stanley, “Multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis of nonstationary time series,” *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, vol. 316, no. 1–4, pp. 87–114, Dec. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0378-4371(02)01383-3.
- [20] M. A. Riley, S. Bonnette, N. Kuznetsov, S. Wallot, and J. Gao, “A tutorial introduction to adaptive fractal analysis,” *Front Physiol*, vol. 3 SEP, 2012, doi: 10.3389/fphys.2012.00371.
- [21] J. Gao, J. Hu, and W. Tung, “Facilitating Joint Chaos and Fractal Analysis of Biosignals through Nonlinear Adaptive Filtering,” *PLoS One*, vol. 6, no. 9, p. e24331, Sep. 2011, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0024331.
- [22] J. J. Collins, C. J. De Luca, A. Burrows, and L. A. Lipsitz, “Age-related changes in open-loop and closed-loop postural control mechanisms,” *Exp Brain Res*, vol. 104, no. 3, pp. 480–492, Jun. 1995, doi: 10.1007/BF00231982.

